

APPENDIX B. HACKTHEBUSINESS SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS¹

Communication materials	Campaign	Description
<p>The logo features the ENTREPRENEDU rainbow arch logo at the top, followed by the word 'ENTREPRENEDU' in blue, and 'HackTheBusiness ITALY' in red below it.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Official logo</p>

¹ All social media visuals were developed in two sizes: 1920x1080px (applicable for LinkedIn, Facebook, X) and 1080x1080px (applicable for Instagram).

<p>The image shows a social media content template for LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram. It features the ENTREPRENEU logo at the top left and the tagline 'Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education' at the top right. The main text includes a note about editing, a call to action for a webinar, the date and time (MAY 30 5-6 PM CET), a link (https://bit.ly/3MBMIY2), and a list of hashtags: #ENTREPRENEU, #hackathon2023, #hackathon, #HorizonEU, #events, #EUinnovationEcosystems, #entrepreneurship, #education, and #innovation. It also includes a Twitter section with similar text and a 'Funded by the European Union' logo at the bottom left.</p>		<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Social Media content templates for Partners</p>
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	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Social Media Visual - Webinar promotion</p>
	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Social Media Visual</p>

<p>We are looking for innovative ideas around these DeepTech areas. Have one? Apply today at entreprenedu.eu</p> <p>ENTREPRENEDU HackTheBusiness ITALY</p> <p>SPACE FOOD CLIMATE</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Social Media Visual</p>
<p>HackTheBusiness Italy is looking for innovative ideas and business solutions around DeepTech within the following challenges:</p> <p>SPACE FOOD CLIMATE</p> <p>Start coding!</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Social Media Visual</p>

<p>ENTREPRENEDU Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education</p> <p>HackTheBusiness ITALY HACKATHON 15-17 June, Rimini Expo Centre, Rimini</p> <p>Apply individually or as a team* and get access to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business acceleration programme Mentoring programme Networking opportunities Professional growth Visibility and recognition Interdisciplinary skills Prizes <p>Let the hacking begin!</p> <p>Registrations open until 15 May 2023 at 17:00 Brussels</p> <p><small>* European individuals aged between 18 and 40 years and/or start-ups based in low/moderate innovation regions established after March 2022 or in incubation phase.</small></p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Postcard - Front</p>
<p>HackTheBusiness Italy is looking for innovative ideas and business solutions around DeepTech within the following challenges:</p> <p>SPACE FOOD CLIMATE</p> <p>Start coding!</p> <p>in t f @ @ENTREPRENEDU JOIN OUR NEWSLETTER</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p> <p>Fraunhofer eban CLEANTECH LUISS f3 PIRELLA GOMMA</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Postcard - Back</p>

HackTheBusiness Italy

Banner

<p style="text-align: center;">E-mail template to ENTREPRENEU partners</p> <p>Subject line: ENTREPRENEU Your help is needed to disseminate HackTheBusiness - Italy</p> <p>Body text: Dear partners,</p> <p>I hope this email finds you well.</p> <p>As a partner of the ENTREPRENEU, I would like to ask your help to disseminate the first hackathon organised by the consortium: HackTheBusiness - Italy.</p> <p>HackTheBusiness - Italy is an entrepreneurship challenge for young minds and start-ups recently established to learn, explore and discover the secrets of deeptech business in the food, climate and space sectors.</p> <p>Registrations to HackTheBusiness - Italy are open until 15 May at 17:00 CEST here.</p> <p>Could you help us disseminate this great event through a blog post, on social media, or in your newsletter? We would really appreciate it!</p> <p>Here you can find a kit with different communication materials. Feel free to use them:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A text suggestion and visuals for social media• Press Release• Banner• Postcard• Event logos <p>Any questions or doubts, please don't hesitate to contact us. Thank you in advance,</p> <p>[NAME]</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Email Template</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">E-mail template to partner from sister projects</p> <p>Subject line: Request to [PARTNER PROJECT NAME]: Your help is needed to disseminate HackTheBusiness - Italy</p> <p>Body text: Dear [NAME],</p> <p>As a partner of [PARTNER PROJECT NAME], I would like to ask your help to disseminate an event that can be of interest to your project community: HackTheBusiness - Italy.</p> <p>ENTREPRENEU is the initiative funded under the Horizon Europe programme, which assembles innovation stakeholders and educational entities from 6 different European countries: (Italy, Bulgaria, Greece, Belgium, Germany and Ireland) with an aim to enhance European entrepreneurial ecosystems for education.</p> <p>HackTheBusiness - Italy, which will take place in Rimini, Italy, between 15-17 June 2023, is an entrepreneurship challenge for young minds and start-ups recently established to learn, explore and discover the secrets of deeptech business in the food, climate and space sectors.</p> <p>Registrations to HackTheBusiness - Italy are open until 15 May at 17:00 CEST here.</p> <p>Could you help us disseminate this great event through a blog post, on social media, or in your newsletter? We would really appreciate it!</p> <p>Here you can find a kit with different communication materials. Feel free to use them:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A text suggestion and visuals for social media • Press Release • Banner • Postcard • Project logos <p>Any questions or doubts, please don't hesitate to contact us. Thank you in advance,</p> <p>[NAME]</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Email Template</p>
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HackTheBusiness Italy

Event materials:
Badges - Participants

	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy</p>	<p>Event materials: Badges - Organisers</p>
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HackTheBusiness Italy

Event materials:
Notebook cover

<p>HackTheBusiness HACKATHON GREECE</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Official logo</p>
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<p>The image shows a social media content template for HackTheBusiness Greece. It features the ENTREPRENEU logo and tagline at the top. The main text includes a note about editing, a call to action for LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram, and a detailed announcement for the second HackTheBusiness in Greece challenge. It mentions that applications are now officially open and provides a link to the application page. There are also social media icons for LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram, and a Twitter section with similar text. At the bottom, there is a logo for 'Funded by the European Union'.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Social Media content templates for Partners</p>
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<p>HackTheBusiness GREECE 25 November, Athens</p> <p>If you are between 18 and 40 years old, based in Europe, with a passion for SPACE - we are waiting for you!</p> <p>Apply today at entreprenedu.eu</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Social Media Visual</p>
<p>HackTheBusiness GREECE 25 November, Athens</p> <p>ENTREPRENEDU Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education</p> <p>APPLY TODAY! entreprenedu.eu</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Social Media Visual</p>

	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Banner</p>
	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Banner</p>

HackTheBusiness Greece

Banner

	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Social Media content templates for Local organisers</p>
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ENTREPRENEDU
HackTheBusiness
HACKATHON GREECE

1ST PHASE
03-05 November 2023
University of Thessaly, Innovation & Entrepreneurship Unit

Apply individually or as a team* and get access to:

- Transform your innovative idea into a business plan through a 3-day competition with recognized mentors & jury
- Be selected to pitch your idea to an international jury (25 November 2023, Athens)
- Be one of the 4-winning teams, selected to be part of the Innovative Mentoring & Coaching Programme promoted by ENTREPRENEDU consortium

Let's HackTheBusiness together!

* European individuals aged between 18 and 40 years and/ or start-ups based in low/moderate innovation regions established after October 2022 or in incubation phase.
Registrations open until 02 November 2023 at 17:00 CET

HackTheBusiness - Greece is looking for innovative ideas and business solutions for SPACE

JOIN OUR NEWSLETTER

Partners: European Union, PIRAEUS, Urban, CLEARTECH, LISS, etc.

HackTheBusiness Greece

Postcard - Local organiser

ENTREPRENEU
HackTheBusiness
HACKATHON GREECE

1ST PHASE
03-05 November 2023
Technical University of Crete

ΠΑΝΤΕΧΝΙΚΟ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ
TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY
OF CRETE

Apply individually or as a team* and get access to:

- Transform your innovative idea into a business plan through a 3-day competition with recognized mentors & jury
- Be selected to pitch your idea to an international jury (25 November 2023, Athens)
- Be one of the 5-winning teams selected to be part of the innovative Mentoring & Coaching Programme promoted by ENTREPRENEU consortium

Let's HackTheBusiness together!

* European individuals aged between 18 and 40 years and/ or start-ups based in low/moderate innovation regions established after October 2022 or in incubation phase.
Registrations open until 02 November 2023 at 17:00 CET

HackTheBusiness - Greece is looking for innovative ideas and business solutions for SPACE

Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, LinkedIn icons | @ENTREPRENEU

JOIN OUR NEWSLETTER

Logos: European Union, H2020, H2021, H2022, H2023, H2024, H2025, H2026, H2027, H2028, H2029, H2030, H2031, H2032, H2033, H2034, H2035, H2036, H2037, H2038, H2039, H2040

HackTheBusiness Greece

Postcard - Local organiser

ENTREPRENEU
HackTheBusiness
HACKATHON **GREECE**

1ST PHASE
03-05 November 2023

National Technical University
of Athens, School of Rural, Surveying
and Geoinformatics Engineering

Apply individually or as a team* and get access to:

- Transform your innovative idea into a business plan through a 3-day competition with recognised mentors & jury.
- Be selected to pitch your idea to an international jury (25 November 2023, Athens).
- Be one of the 4-winning teams selected to be part of the innovative Mentoring & Coaching Programme promoted by ENTREPRENEU consortium.

Let's HackTheBusiness together!

* European individuals aged between 16 and 44 years and/ or start-ups based in low/moderate innovation regions established after October 2022 or in incubation phase.
Registrations open until 02 November 2023 at 17:00 CET

HackTheBusiness - Greece is looking for innovative ideas and business solutions for SPACE

JOIN OUR NEWSLETTER

Logos: European Union, Entrepreneurship, eBan, CLEARATHON, UASS, FORTH, COVA

HackTheBusiness Greece

Postcard - Local organiser

ENTREPRENEU
HackTheBusiness
HACKATHON GREECE

1ST PHASE
03-05 November 2023
Thinc Thrace incubator,
Democritus University of Thrace

Apply individually or as a team* and get access to:

- Transform your innovative idea into a business plan through a 3-day competition with recognized mentors & jury
- Be selected to pitch your idea to an international jury (25 November 2023, Athens)
- Be one of the 4-winning teams selected to be part of the Innovative Mentoring & Coaching Programme promoted by ENTREPRENEU consortium

Let's HackTheBusiness together!

* European individuals aged between 16 and 40 years and/ or start-ups based in low/moderate innovation regions established after October 2022 or in incubation phase.
Registrations open until 02 November 2023 at 17:00 CET

HackTheBusiness - Greece is looking for innovative ideas and business solutions for SPACE

JOIN OUR NEWSLETTER

Funded by the European Union

ENTREPRENEU, eCUB, CLEANTECH NETWORK, LISS, FEMTECH, COVA

HackTheBusiness Greece

Postcard - Local organiser

The poster is divided into two main sections. The top section, titled '1ST PHASE 03-05 November 2023', features logos for ENTREPRENEU, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, and walk. It lists three benefits of applying: transforming ideas into business plans, pitching to an international jury, and participating in a mentoring program. A QR code is provided for registration. The bottom section, titled 'HackTheBusiness - Greece is looking for innovative ideas and business solutions for SPACE', features an illustration of astronauts and a space station. It includes social media handles for @ENTREPRENEU, a newsletter sign-up link, and logos of partner organizations like the European Union, Fraunhofer, CleanTech, and others.

HackTheBusiness Greece

Postcard - Local organiser

<p>The banner features a colorful striped background with a globe at the top. It includes the ENTREPRENEDU logo, HackTheBusiness HACKATHON GREECE logo, and the University of Thessaly logo. The text reads: "1ST PHASE 03-05 November 2023 University of Thessaly, Innovation & Entrepreneurship Unit". A small European Union logo is also present.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Banner - Local organiser</p>
<p>The banner features a colorful striped background with a globe at the top. It includes the ENTREPRENEDU logo, HackTheBusiness HACKATHON GREECE logo, and the Technical University of Crete logo. The text reads: "1ST PHASE 03-05 November 2023 Technical University of Crete". A small European Union logo is also present.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Banner - Local organiser</p>

<p>The banner features a background of vertical stripes in blue, orange, and red. At the top, it includes the ENTREPRENEU logo, the HackTheBusiness HACKATHON GREECE logo, and the logo of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). The central text reads '1ST PHASE 03-05 November 2023' and 'National Technical University of Athens, School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering'. On the left, there is an illustration of an astronaut and the European Union flag with the text 'Funded by the European Union'.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Banner - Local organiser</p>
<p>The banner features a background of vertical stripes in blue, orange, and red. At the top, it includes the ENTREPRENEU logo, the HackTheBusiness HACKATHON GREECE logo, the Thinc Thrace incubator logo, and the logo of Democritus University of Thrace. The central text reads '1ST PHASE 03-05 November 2023' and 'Thinc Thrace incubator, Democritus University of Thrace'. On the left, there is an illustration of an astronaut and the European Union flag with the text 'Funded by the European Union'.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Banner - Local organiser</p>

<p>The banner features a colorful background with vertical stripes in blue, orange, and red. At the top, it includes the ENTREPRENEU logo, the text 'HackTheBusiness HACKATHON GREECE', the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki logo, the 'walk' logo, and the AUTH Innovation Accelerator logo. The central text reads '1ST PHASE 03-05 November 2023' and 'Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Walk AUTH Innovation Accelerator and SpaceDot'. A small illustration of an astronaut is on the left, and the European Union logo is at the bottom left.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Banner - Local organiser</p>
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<p>The poster features the ENTREPRENEDU logo at the top left. The main title is 'HackTheBusiness HACKATHON GREECE' with 'GREECE' in a red pill-shaped box, followed by '25 November, Athens'. Below this is a central banner with a colorful vertical striped background, an illustration of an astronaut, and the text 'Let's HackTheBusiness together'. At the bottom, there are social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube, followed by '@ENTREPRENEDU'. To the right, it says 'JOIN OUR NEWSLETTER' with a QR code. The footer contains logos for 'Funded by the European Union', 'EUREKA', 'Fraunhofer', 'eBan', 'CLEANTECH BULGARIA', 'LUISS', 'FES', 'TRESALT', and 'cordlife'.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Event materials: One-page postcard</p>
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	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Event materials: Two-pages postcard</p>
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HackTheBusiness Greece

Event materials:
Notebook cover

HackTheBusiness Greece

Event materials:
Tote bag

	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Event materials: Pens</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">E-mail template to ENTREPRENEU partners</p> <p>Subject line: [ENTREPRENEU] Your help is needed to disseminate HackTheBusiness - Greece</p> <p>Body text: Dear partners,</p> <p>I hope this email finds you well.</p> <p>As a partner of the ENTREPRENEU project, I would like to ask your help to disseminate the second hackathon organised by the consortium: HackTheBusiness - Greece.</p> <p>HackTheBusiness - Greece is an entrepreneurship challenge for young minds and start-ups recently established to learn, explore and discover the secrets of space technologies.</p> <p>Registrations to HackTheBusiness - Greece are open until 02 November at 17:00 CET here.</p> <p>Could you help us disseminate this great event through a blog post, on social media, or in your newsletter? We would really appreciate it!</p> <p>Here you can find a kit with different communication materials. Feel free to use and adapt them:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A text suggestion and visuals for social media • Press Release • Banner • Postcard • Event logos <p>Any questions or doubts, please don't hesitate to contact us.</p> <p>Thank you in advance for your cooperation and help.</p> <p>[NAME]</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Email Template</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">E-mail template to partner from sister projects</p> <p>Subject line: [ENTREPRENEU] Request to [PARTNER PROJECT NAME]: Your help is needed to disseminate HackTheBusiness - Greece</p> <p>Body text: Dear [NAME],</p> <p>As a partner of [PARTNER PROJECT NAME], I would like to ask your help to disseminate an event that can be of interest to your project community: HackTheBusiness - Greece.</p> <p>ENTREPRENEU is the initiative funded under the Horizon Europe programme, which assembles innovation stakeholders and educational entities from 6 different European countries: (Italy, Bulgaria, Greece, Belgium, Germany and Ireland) with an aim to enhance European entrepreneurial ecosystems for education.</p> <p>HackTheBusiness - Greece is an entrepreneurship challenge for young minds and start-ups recently established to learn, explore and discover the secrets of space technologies.</p> <p>Registrations to HackTheBusiness - Greece are open until 02 November at 17:00 CET here.</p> <p>Could you help us disseminate this great event through a blog post, on social media, or in your newsletter? We would really appreciate it!</p> <p>Here you can find a kit with different communication materials. Feel free to use and adapt them:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A text suggestion and visuals for social media • Press Release • Banner • Postcard • Project logos <p>Any questions or doubts, please don't hesitate to contact us. Thank you in advance,</p> <p>[NAME]</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Email Template</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">E-mail template to local organisers</p> <p>Subject line: [ENTREPRENEU] HackTheBusiness Greece - Media Kit and important information</p> <p>Body text: Dear All,</p> <p>As a local organiser of HackTheBusiness - Greece, I would like to share with you a few essential steps and links for a proper dissemination of the activity.</p> <p>All activities from the promotion campaign should lead to the main webpage of the event https://entrepredu.eu/hackthebusinessgreece/. Here potential participants will have access to the main information on the event and link to the registration page (managed by F6S).</p> <p>We suggest that every post from your institution's social media pages should include a link to ENTREPRENEU socials and specific hashtags.</p> <p><u>ENTREPRENEU social media:</u></p> <p>Facebook Twitter LinkedIn Instagram</p> <p><u>Hashtags:</u></p> <p>Mandatory: #entrepredu #HackTheBusiness #htbgreece Optional: #HorizonEU #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space</p> <p>Registrations to HackTheBusiness - Greece are open until 02 November 2023 at 17:00 CET here.</p> <p>Here you can find a media kit with different communication materials. Feel free to use and adapt them:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A text suggestion and visuals for social media • Press Release • Newsletter banner • Postcard • HackTheBusiness Greece logos <p>You can find more information on ENTREPRENEU branding in the attached ppt.</p> <p>Any questions or doubts, please don't hesitate to contact us. Thank you in advance for your cooperation and help.</p> <p>[NAME]</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Greece</p>	<p>Email Template</p>
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<p>HackTheBusiness HACKATHON BULGARIA</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Official logo</p>
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<p>The image shows a social media content template for HackTheBusiness Bulgaria. It features the ENTREPRENEDU logo and tagline at the top. The main text includes a note about editing, a call to action for LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram, and a detailed announcement about the final #HackTheBusiness competition in Bulgaria. It mentions that the competition is for young minds who wish to transform innovative and sustainable ideas into real businesses. The text describes the competition as a "not-to-miss" opportunity for students, early-stage startups, and researchers to gain extra experience, network with experts, and level-up their professional careers while having fun. Applications are now officially open, with a link to entrepredu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/. It encourages users to grab their place today and use #HackTheBusiness in Bulgaria. It also asks users to follow @ENTREPRENEDU for more information and lists the following hashtags: #ENTREPRENEDU #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria #Entrepreneurship #Innovation #Sustainability. A Twitter section follows, with a call to action: "Ready to shape a #sustainable future? Join us at #HackTheBusiness in Bulgaria! Calling all #students and early-stage #startups - unleash your creativity and entrepreneurial skills. Applications open now!" with a link to the same website. The info line is: "Info: @ENTREPRENEDU #Entrepreneurship #Innovation #Sustainability". At the bottom left, there is a logo for "Funded by the European Union".</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Social media content templates for Partners</p>
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<p>The banner features the ENTREPRENEDEDU logo at the top left. To its right, the text reads 'HackTheBusiness HACKATHON BULGARIA' with 'BULGARIA' in a red rounded rectangle, followed by '26 & 27 March, Sofia'. Below this is an illustration of a man with glasses and a blue shirt sitting at a laptop in a forest. A speech bubble next to him says 'Have a sustainable & innovative idea?'. At the bottom, there is a row of logos including the European Union, Fraunhofer, reban, CLEANTECH BULGARIA, LUISS, IFS, and coralia.</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Banner</p>
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	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Banner</p>
	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Social media visual</p>

<p>HackTheBusiness BULGARIA 26 & 27 March, Sofia</p> <p>ENTREPRENEU Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education</p> <p>APPLY TODAY! entrepreneu.eu</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Social media visual</p>
<p>HackTheBusiness BULGARIA</p> <p>If you are between 18 and 40 years old, based in Europe, with a passion for SUSTAINABILITY - we are waiting for you!</p> <p>Apply today at entrepreneu.eu</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Social media visual</p>

	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Social media visual</p>
	<p>HackTheBusiness Bulgaria</p>	<p>Social media visual</p>

HackTheBusiness Bulgaria

Social media visual

HackTheBusiness Bulgaria

Event materials:
Badges - Organisers

HackTheBusiness Bulgaria

Event materials:
Badges - Participants